

An Open-source Framework for Time-domain Simulations

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ABSTRACT

In scientific research simulation of new or existing acoustical models is typically implemented using commercial numerical programming environments like Simulink/Matlab or expensive simulation packages like COMSOL or FLUENT. In this paper a new version of the open-source simulation library ART (Acoustic Research Tool) is presented where time-domain simulation capabilities have now been added to existing frequency domain models. The concept allows mixing of modeling elements belonging to different levels of abstraction and it relieves the user from tricky implementation details like scheduling, data dependencies and memory allocation. Starting with an equation in the z-Domain, signals can be described recursively as a function of other current or previous signal samples and local or global simulation parameters. Alternatively signals can also be generated by specifying a certain topology of predefined elements with certain input and output ports. The library can be called from any programming environment running on Microsoft Windows or on Linux which allows it to be integrated in any application software project. The examples shown here have been written in the open-source high-level programming language Python. They can be downloaded together with the library and documentation from the project site <http://artool.sourceforge.net>.

1. INTRODUCTION

The simulation and verification of acoustical models is usually done in commercial environments like Simulink/Matlab or implemented in a high-level programming language such as Java or Python. However, none of these tools perfectly fulfill the requirements of acoustical simulations, namely easy usage and extensibility. The Acoustic Research Tool, abbreviated *ART* was originally developed as an open-source library for frequency-domain simulations of acoustical models, see [1]. In 2012, ART was extended in order to allow users the possibility to do any kind of time-domain simulation. Although the focus of course lies on acoustical models, the implemented architecture provides the functionality of implementing any kind of signal

processing in the time-domain.

The structure of this paper is the following: Section 2 presents a short overview of the history of ART and the previously existing features which could be reused for time-domain simulations. In Section 3, the overall architecture of the new simulator as well as some internal data structures are explained. Moreover, it gives an overview of the implemented acoustical models which are available in the simulation library. Two examples are presented in Section 4, one using modules from the previously mentioned library, the other showing the flexibility of ART to simulate acoustical models which are not available in the current library by the usage of generic time modules.

2. OVERVIEW OF ART

2.1 History of ART

ART is a platform-independent open-source library which provides users the ability to simulate existing models in the frequency-domain and to implement custom elements which can be added to the simulation. It was initiated by Wilfried Kausel in 2005 and has been under development since then. Over the last years, several contributors have added new simulation methods and optimized the simulation process. However, ART only covered frequency-domain simulations and thus only allowed to calculate impedances of musical instruments, but no sound synthesis.

During 2012, ART was extended in order to enable time-domain simulations for sound-synthesis and acoustical model simulation. Generally speaking, models in the time-domain can be based on any discrete signal or function and are thus not restricted to specific building blocks such as finite impulse response (FIR) filters. Consequently, an open approach had to be chosen giving users a means to make simulations on existing models and functions, but also implement their own time models without the need of recompiling any source code. ART is implemented in ANSI C++ and can be compiled with either commercial (e.g., MS Visual Studio) or open-source (e.g., GNU Compiler Collection) compilers on any platform. The output is either an executable or a dynamic library which allows the integration of ART into nearly all common high-level programming languages (current examples on the homepage make use of Delphi and Python).

2.2 Comparison to other Simulation Environments

Simulations of acoustical circuits are usually done in high level programming languages or simulation environments

such as Matlab/Simulink, Python or C++. Moreover, there also exist several other scientific open-source projects like FAUST (Functional Audio Stream, [2]) or EIN as presented by Lansky and Steiglitz in [3]. In [4], Rabenstein et al. present a simulation approach, which is very similar to the one implemented by ART. They also use generic physical blocks with input and output ports and present a solution for the automatic dependency calculation.

ART is currently in an early development stage and not using any optimizations when compiled. Therefore, any comparison between the performance of ART with professional simulation environments like Matlab cannot seriously be conducted. It provides a library of well-known acoustical models in the frequency as well as in the time domain and can easily be integrated in every other high-level programming language. Thus, ART should not be seen as an alternative but rather an addition to traditional simulation environments because the user can focus on the physical model without the need of learning a new programming language or low-level programming.

2.3 Existing Simulation Framework

The previous version of ART already provided a set of functionality which could be reused for the implementation of time-domain simulations. First of all, *muParserX* [5], an open-source parsing library which provides a subset of Matlab or GNU Octave, was integrated into ART to set values of several simulation variables. Although not all of the features of the parser were extensively used, it made value assignments for variables much more flexible. For example, assignment expressions could contain complex mathematical formulas and even reference values of other variables.

The second important feature implemented in the frequency domain simulation was the creation of a *dependency graph* which is responsible for the following two points:

- (1) Checking for circular variable or expression references
- (2) Intelligent evaluation of expressions

Both functionalities may be easily demonstrated with an example: Assuming we want to calculate the wavelength of a given frequency, but also take the current temperature into account. Wavelength λ is based on the speed of sound c and frequency f :

$$\lambda = \frac{c}{f} \tag{1}$$

The speed of sound c depends on temperature T (in Celsius) as described in the following equation (see Equation(16) in [6]):

$$c \cong 20.06 \cdot \sqrt{T + 273.15} \tag{2}$$

If temperature T changes, the speed of sound and therefore also the wavelength have to be recalculated. ART therefore builds the previously mentioned dependency graph as shown in Figure 1 in order to efficiently evaluate expressions: If any of the variables gets assigned a new value or a new calculation expression, all dependent variables will

be set invalid and reevaluated the next time the value is needed. This graph also detects cyclic dependencies, e.g., when c was defined by

$$c = \frac{\lambda}{f} \tag{3}$$

instead of Equation (1). When ART is triggered to evaluate λ , it will first try to calculate c . However, in order to get the value of c , λ has to be evaluated, thus resulting in an indefinite loop. ART automatically throws an exception any time such a cyclic dependency occurs during an evaluation. This is implemented by a simple flag which is set before the beginning of the evaluation and cleared after the value assignment has completed. Whenever ART tries to evaluate a variable with this flag set, a circular dependency has occurred.

ART also implements basic error handling, e.g., when there is a syntax error for an expression. The exception thrown by *muParserX* will be handled by ART and the error message passed to the calling function. The same is true for some exceptions specific to ART, e.g., the previously mentioned circular dependency. It is expected to improve the error-handling in future releases in order to simplify the debugging process for the user.

Figure 1. Dependency graph of wavelength variable λ .

3. IMPLEMENTATION OF TIME-DOMAIN SIMULATIONS

The previous section described the provided features by ART for frequency-domain simulations. Although these functions are quite useful for all kinds of simulations, time-domain simulations require additional data types and adaptations of existing interfaces and methods. This section first gives an overview of the newly implemented architecture in the time domain. After that, the two main functions to enable efficient simulations are discussed, namely resizable ring buffers and an easy-to-use convolution function. At the end of the section, the current state of implemented time-domain modules is shortly presented.

3.1 Architectural Overview of Time-domain Modules

A time-domain simulation consists of global parameters such as the sampling period T and several modules. These

are added to the simulator and can be connected to each other. Figure 2 shows the template of such a time-domain module: It has a unique name, has the ability to save local parameters and consists of a number of input and output ports. Output ports save the prescribed calculation expression and may reference any global or local parameters as well as input and output ports of the current time module. Input ports only reference to output ports of other time-domain modules, but do not implement any calculations. Note that each output port cannot only access past time values from other input and output ports of the same module, but also past time values of itself (i.e., a difference equation) like it is the case for infinite impulse response (IIR) filters.

Figure 2. Basic idea of the time module concept: Each time module has a unique name, n input and m output ports. The time module may be seen as a black box – the calculation details of the ports are hidden from the user.

The generic black box is a template for any time-domain module and is implemented as an interface. It provides access to read out the current value of the output ports, associate input ports with output ports of other time modules and set local parameters. All modules can access global simulation parameters which opens the door to change usually fixed input values like the sound velocity during a simulation without much effort.

3.2 Resizable Ring Buffers and Convolution

As already mentioned, output ports may access a time step of any other port of its own module as long as this time step is not in the future. The naive way of implementing this functionality is to provide an array consisting of enough elements to save all values for the complete simulation. When simulating only 10 seconds for a sampling rate of 44.1 kHz including several modules with multiple input and output ports may thus quickly result in shortage of memory. A common solution to solve this problem is to use ring buffers as shown in Figure 3. As most acoustical models in the time-domain do not require filters of high order, a ring buffer with 10 to 20 elements will fit for usual applications and thus highly reduce memory usage.

However, some applications even require an automatic resizing of the ring-buffer. This is the case, e.g., for the discrete convolution which is commonly used in digital signal processing and defined by

$$y[t] = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} u[k] \cdot g[t - k] = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} u[t - k] \cdot g[k]. \quad (4)$$

Figure 3. Accessing an element of a ring buffer of size 12: The inner circle shows the elements from index 0 to 11, whereas the outer circle starts from 12 and ends with 23. When accessing the 14th element, the ring buffer in fact returns element number $14 \bmod 12 = 2$.

Assuming that $g[t]$ is a finite transfer function with a fixed number of elements, the user usually has to make sure that the input function $u[t]$ consists of at least the same number of elements as $g[t]$. In case $u[t]$ will be convoluted with multiple transfer functions, the number of needed buffer elements is not easily determined and a common source of mistakes. In ART, this problem was solved with a resizable ring buffer which automatically increments the buffer size of an input function if the number of unused elements gets near a defined threshold. Consequently, the user only needs to define the correct mathematical model and does not need to deal with any implementation details. The description of the resize function of the ring buffer and the internal implementation of the convolution function can be found in [7].

3.3 Time-domain Module Library

One target of the time-domain simulator in ART was to provide a generic simulation library for any kind of discrete signal processing, not only limited to acoustical applications.¹ This is the reason why in the current version three types of modules have been implemented:

- (1) General-purpose signal processing modules
- (2) Digital Waveguide (DWG) modules of common acoustical elements
- (3) Generic time module

The first type of modules covers simple mathematical functions like adding two input signals or a signal generating module for a single impulse or sine wave. The advantage of this kind of modules is that the user does not need to implement this modules on his or her own and they automatically generate proper signals for the globally defined sampling rate. For example, the sine wave module has three local parameters which can be set by the user:

¹ Note that there is no general rule about how acoustical models look like. In contrary, they are based on mathematical models of other disciplines like electrical engineering or mechanics.

amplitude, frequency (in Hz) and a phase delay given in seconds.

The second type of modules covers DWGs for cylindrical and conical bores as well as cylindrical and conical junctions as first presented in [8] and later evaluated, e.g., in [9]. However, ART currently does not provide any models which take viscothermal losses into account. The cylindrical bore module is based on a fractional delay filter – the user just has to specify the length the cylinder and the type of interpolation filter, namely Thiran or Lagrange. ART automatically calculates the correct filter parameters based on the selected type, the current sampling rate and the specified sound velocity.² Both types of fractional delay filters including stability considerations are presented in [10]. The cylindrical junction module is used to simulate wave scattering effects between any two cylindrical bores with different radii.

Figure 4. Parameter overview of the DWG cone module. The user has to provide both cone apex radii r_1 and r_2 whereas the $length$ parameter will be automatically calculated by ART.

The conical modules are more complex as they usually include the calculation of the cone apex radii as can be seen in Figure 4. Therefore, ART provides an alternative way of specifying the parameters of the cone as bore profile (radius on the left end, radius on the right end and length of the cone), see Figure 5. Like the cylindrical junction module, the conical junction module calculates the wave scattering between two cones or a cone and a cylinder with different radii.³ Again, the user has two different ways of specifying the parameters, one with the cone apex radii and the spherical area of both cones at the junction, the other with the left and right radius as well as the length of the conical bores at the left and right side of the junction. Section 4.3 will present a small simulation with nearly all of the described DWG modules.

So far, the user could only refer to pre-implemented modules and only had little possibility to individualize them. This is the reason why the third type of modules has been introduced: The generic time module allows the user to create new input and output ports and define calculation

² Fractional delay filters are used to interpolate values between any two time samples. As the spatial resolution of the simulation depends on the sampling rate and sound velocity, you can also use them to interpolate values between two spatial samples. Thus, the length of a cylindrical bore can be set to any value and does not need to be a multiple of the spatial resolution.

³ The term *radius* in this context refers to the apex radius and not the radius at the junction between both elements.

Figure 5. Alternative parameter specification of the cone module based on the left radius r_1 , the right radius r_2 and the length of the cone $length$.

expression for them. They fully integrate with all other modules, but are more flexible and can even be used to solve difference equations or discretized differential equations.

All presented modules can be created by using the interface of ART without the need of re-compiling the library or implementing C++ code. However, the architecture of ART also allows other programmers to easily integrate new modules to the existing ones, giving them the full power of object oriented programming concepts. It is a future goal to engage other scientists to implement other acoustical models (e.g., Wave Digital Filters) and make them available to the users of ART.

4. EXAMPLES

This section gives an overview of the flexibility of ART and demonstrates how it eases the simulation in case of pre-implemented modules. Note that the focus lies on the implementation of the simulation in ART and not the mathematical theory which is presented in detail in the given literature.

4.1 Fibonacci Numbers

Although the Fibonacci numbers are no physical model, they are a good means of demonstrating the power and flexibility of ART. The standard definition of the Fibonacci numbers is given by

$$f_n = f_{n-1} + f_{n-2} \tag{5}$$

meaning that the current element is the sum of the previous two elements. Moreover, the most common definition sets the first element to zero and the second to one:

$$f_1 = 0, f_2 = 1 \tag{6}$$

For linear recursion equations like the Fibonacci numbers, there is an explicit formula to calculate an element without the need of knowing all previous elements. However, like for some types of non-linear differential equations, it is not always possible to find an explicit solution for a general (non-linear) difference equation. Thus, it is necessary to calculate each element separately in order to get the solution of the n^{th} element.

```

# init simulation
pSim = ARTRootObject()

# create simulator
mySim = ARTCreateSimulator("MySimulator", "TimeDomain", "")

# create time module
timeModule = ARTCreateTModule(mySim, "FibonacciModule", "TimeModule")

# add output ports to time modules
ARTAddOPortToTModule(timeModule, "fib", "fib[t] = fib[t-1] + fib[t-2]")

# initialize fibonacci ports
ARTSetParameter(mySim, "FibonacciModule.fib[-1] = 1; FibonacciModule.fib[-2] = 0")

fibPort = ARTGetPortFromTModule(FibonacciModule, "fib")

# print fibonacci numbers
for i in range(0, 47):
    # get data structure
    fibonacci = ARTGetComplexFromPort(fibPort, i + 3)
    print "fib[{0:2d}] = {1:.0f}".format(i, fibonacci.re)

# destroy all previously allocated elements
ARTRootDestroy()

```

Figure 6. Calculation of the first 50 elements of the Fibonacci numbers in ART by using the generic time module.

Figure 6 shows a complete implementation of calculating the Fibonacci numbers in ART using the open-source programming language Python. In the first line, a so called *ARTRootObject* is created. This element is responsible for the complete memory administration of the simulation and contains all used simulators, modules and internal data structures. The user does not need to track any allocated objects as they will all be freed in the last line by calling the *ARTRootDestroy* function. After the creation of the root object, a time-domain simulator is added – note that you have to explicitly define the simulation domain as ART is also capable of creating a simulator in the frequency domain. The next steps are straight forward: a generic time-domain module with one output port is added to the simulator. The output port *fib* just contains the definition of the Fibonacci numbers and is initialized by the *ARTSetParameter* function. Note that the simulation starts at time $t = 0$ such that the first two elements are treated like past time values for $t = -1$ and $t = -2$. The last part of the example code retrieves the current value from the port using the *ARTGetComplexFromPort* function and prints the result on the standard output in a for-loop.

Although the calculation of the Fibonacci numbers could have been done much easier, this example shall demonstrate the usage and flexibility of ART: First, the user does not need to know anything about the calculation itself; if an output port depends on other values, these are determined automatically. Secondly, the user does not need to allocate any memory – ART automatically allocates the amount of memory needed. Even when calculating 1000 or more elements of the Fibonacci numbers, only the last 20 elements are kept in memory. Finally, the user could introduce several local parameters and other time modules to simulate much more complex acoustical models. Consequently, users do not need profound knowledge of programming in order to implement and simulate new models.

4.2 Numerical Solution of Differential Equations

This section only shows how ART can be used to even solve differential equations, but will not go into details on the mathematical background which can be found in [7].

The differential equation which will be numerically solved is given by

$$y''(t) + 2y'(t) + 5y(t) = t \quad (7)$$

with the known values

$$y(0) = 1, y'(0) = 0. \quad (8)$$

Using the method of finite differences, Equation 7 can be solved numerically with the following difference equation where T represents the sampling period:

$$y[t] = \frac{2y[t-1](1+T) - y[t-2] + T^3 \cdot t}{1 + 2T + 5T^2}. \quad (9)$$

Figure 7 shows the solution in ART including the initialization of $y[-1]$ and $y[-2]$ which is done using the *ARTSetParameter* function. At a sampling rate of 1 KHz, the numerical error to the exact solution is below 10^{-3} and converges towards 0.

4.3 Conical Bore Simulation

In [9, p 102-109], Walstijn sets up a simulation of conical bores based on DWG modules. The simulated part consists of a cone in the center and a cylinder on each the left and right side of the cone as shown in Figure 8.

The implemented setup of the simulation is slightly different to the original one of Walstijn: Instead of fractional delay modules, the DWG modules presented in Section 3.3 were used,⁴ namely two cylindrical bores, one conical bore and two conical junctions. As previously described,

⁴ Note that the fractional delay filters are implemented as part of the cylindrical and conical bore modules, but don't need to be added separately to the simulation.

```

# create time modules
numericModule = ARTCreateTModule(mySim, "numericSolution", "TimeModule")

# add output ports to time modules
ARTAddOPortToTModule(numericModule, "out",
    "out[t] = (2*out[t-1]*(1+T) - out[t-2] + T^3*t)/(1 + 2*T + 5*T^2)")

# fetch output port from the numeric module
outPort = ARTGetPortFromTModule(numericModule, "out")

# set the global sampling rate to 1kHz
ARTSetParameter(mySim, "T = 1/1000")

# initialize past values of y[t]
ARTSetParameter(mySim, "numericSolution.out[-1] = 1")
ARTSetParameter(mySim, "numericSolution.out[-2] = 1")

for i in range(0, 10000):
    # get data structure
    outVal = ARTGetComplexFromPort(outPort, i)
    # print value to standard output
    print "out[{0:2d}] = {1:.10f}".format(i, outVal.re)

```

Figure 7. Python code for simulating a differential equation with ART. Note that some steps like initialization and deallocation of all objects have been omitted for simplicity.

Figure 8. Measurements of the conical bore simulation. The original simulation can be found in [9, p 102-109].

it was not necessary to calculate any cone apex radii – providing the measurements of the bore profile was sufficient. Figure 10 shows the plotted output of the impulse response of the defined system. The results show high similarity with the plots in [9].

```

# create cone module
cone = ARTCreateTModule(sim, "Cone",
    "DWGConeModule")

# connect output ports of modules
ARTConnectPorts(sim, "LeftConeJunction.
    p2m = Cone.plm; Cone.plp =
    LeftConeJunction.p2p")
ARTConnectPorts(sim, "Cone.p2m =
    RightConeJunction.plm;
    RightConeJunction.plp = Cone.p2p")

# set local parameters of cone module
ARTSetParameter(sim, "Cone.r1 = 0.006;
    Cone.r2 = 0.004; Cone.length = 0.19;
    Cone.mode = 'boreprofile'; Cone.type
    = 'lagrange'")

```

Figure 9. Extract from the conical bore simulation implemented in Python accessing the ART library. The complete code is available in the *example* section on SourceForge, see [1].

Figure 10. Impulse response of the anechoic (open loop) conical bore system with bilinear transformation used at the conical junction modules and Lagrange filters for the delay lines. The sampling frequency was 44.1 kHz, the speed of sound set to 331 m/s.

4.4 Simulation of Brassiness

Another simulation example shall demonstrate the flexibility of ART when using models which are currently not part of the library and covers *brassiness* in a cylindrical tube.

Brassiness is a phenomenon occurring in brass instruments when the volume is above a certain level. The resulting pressure wave includes periodic impulses causing the spectrum to contain high frequencies. This change in the high harmonics can be sensed, e.g., when listening to a recording of a trumpet played at different sound levels.

Brassiness has been studied for a long time and there are several existing models in the frequency domain based on general Burger's equations. In [11], the implementation of brassiness in a complete simulation of a trumpet is presented. Other approaches rely on models in the time domain and take the change of the sound velocity into account. The implemented approach for the simulation of this section is based on [12] where time-dependent delay modules are used to generate the effect, but also takes the fluid velocity into account.

Figure 11. A delay module for the brassiness simulation: The delay value D is calculated based on the sound speed c and velocity difference v .

Figure 11 shows a block diagram of this delay module. When comparing this module with the generic time module in Figure 2, you can easily see the similarities: c and v are local parameters, p_{L+} and p_{R-} are input ports, p_{L-} and p_{R+} are output ports. All output ports and local parameters need explicit calculation expressions and can access past time values. Moreover, ART even allows the user to define simple if-then-else expressions which were used in this simulation to minimize interpolation errors by checking the sign of the current pressure values and use different expressions for each case. The details of this simulation including a description of the physical model and the implementation in ART can be found in [13].

Several other examples of time-domain simulations can be found in [7], including the non-linear simulation of lip movement in brass wind instruments as explained by Adachi and Sato in [14] and the reed movement of a clarinet mouthpiece presented by Chatziioannou and Walstijn in [15, 16].

5. CONCLUSION

In the previous section, several example simulations were presented, demonstrating the implemented features of ART. Although the provided functionality is good enough for small to medium simulation setups, future work will include the implementation of other well-known models in the time domain, increase the usability and performance and provide a proper documentation such that users with only fundamental knowledge in programming will be able to create their own simulations, too. Moreover, support from the open-source community to implement wrapper interfaces to other programming languages and improve the current integration of existing interfaces would be highly appreciated.

The usability of ART can be improved by providing a graphical user interface (GUI) which allows the user to easily set global and local parameters and create new templates for time-domain modules. Apart from the described restrictions, ART could become an interesting supplement to commercial applications like Simulink for time-domain simulations. Moreover, it could also be used for educational and experimental purposes due to its flexibility and

the provided collection of implemented existing acoustical models.

6. REFERENCES

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